

A rapid spectrophotometric method for measuring arsenic in water after enrichment of arsenomolybdate on polyurethane foam and complexation with Rhodamine B

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Abstract : Simple, rapid and accurate spectrophotometric method is presented for the determination of arsenic in water. The method is based on the preconcentration of arsenomolybdate on polyurethane foam followed by its elution in acetone and formation of ion association complex of arsenomolybdate with Rhodamine B. The absorbance of the complex is measured at 560 nm. The colour system obeys Beer's law from 0.5–5.0 ng mL⁻¹ of arsenic. The detection limit has been found to be 0.10 ng mL⁻¹ of As. The molar absorptivity was found to be 2.25×10^6 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Under optimized conditions, the proposed method was applied to the determination of arsenic present in surface and ground water samples collected from lakes and tube wells. The method has been applied successfully to determine arsenic in NIST standard water sample and the result is in good agreement with the certified value.

Keywords : Arsenic, spectrophotometry, preconcentration, polyurethane foam, Rhodamine B.

Introduction

Recently, arsenic has become increasingly important in environmental geochemistry because of its significance for human health. It is widely distributed and human exposure is inevitable. Of the various sources of arsenic in the environment, drinking water probably poses the greatest threat to human health¹. Depending on the local availability, drinking water is derived from varieties of sources such as surface water (river, lakes, reservoirs and ponds), ground water (aquifers) and rain water, which are variable in terms of arsenic risk. Arsenic is highly toxic and can lead to a wide range of health problems. It is carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic^{2,3}. Arsenic is naturally introduced into water by dissolution of minerals and ores and by percolation of ground water through arsenic enriched rocks. Anthropogenic sources of arsenic are wood preservatives, alloying agents and the combination of fossil fuels. Inorganic arsenic occurs in the environment in several forms. In natural water it is mostly found as the trivalent As^{III} arsenite species or the pentavalent arsenate As^V. Following the accumulation of evidence for the chronic toxic effects of arsenic in drinking water, recom-

mended and regulatory arsenic limits of World Health Organization (WHO) and United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) were reduced from 50 to 10 µg/L^{4,5}. According to Indian standard specification limit for arsenic is 50 µg/L⁶. In recent years, there has been growing interest in the analysis and speciation of arsenic (As) species, owing to their high toxicity and abundance in the environment. Hydride generation (HG) is a well known technique for determination of arsenic species in a wide range of samples as has been highlighted by several researchers⁷⁻⁹. A number of analytical techniques based on the HG exist for determination of arsenic are atomic absorption spectrometry¹⁰, atomic emission spectrometry¹¹, atomic fluorescence spectrometry¹², ICP-mass spectrometry¹³, Gas diffusion Flow Injection with electrochemical detection¹⁴ etc. These methods benefit from high sensitivity and low detection limit, but need sophisticated instrumentation, optimization of different parameters and expert hands. On the other hand the spectrophotometric method can be regarded as a simple method that can be used in many commercial laboratories.

Most spectrometric methods for measuring arsenic are

based on the Gutzeit¹⁵ method. The classical approach of this method is based on the generation of arsine gas and quantifying arsenic by trapping it either in a silver diethyldithio carbamate solution¹⁶ or on paper impregnated with mercuric bromide. The Gutzeit method¹⁷ suffers from difficulties in the quantitative evaluation of small quantities of arsine gas. Johnson¹⁸ and Johnson and Pilson¹⁹ first proposed an elegant modification of standard molybdate based method as an alternative to the Gutzeit method. Spectrophotometric method based on the formation of a reduced arsenomolybdate complex is one of the recommended methods for trace level²⁰ of arsenic determination.

It has recently been shown that the extraction by PUF can be used successfully in conjunction with spectrophotometry for the determination of trace elements²¹⁻²⁵. This paper describes extension of this technique to determine arsenic at trace level. The method involves the formation of arsenomolybdate, its extraction by polyether based PUF, elution in acetone, formation of an ion associate of arsenomolybdate with Rhodamine B (RB) and spectrophotometric measurement of absorbance of the coloured complex at 560 nm. The method is convenient, sensitive and precise.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All spectral measurements were performed with a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 45 spectrophotometer equipped with 10 mm matched cells having a wavelength range of 190–1100 nm. An Orion research model 720A+ pH meter was used for pH measurement. A soxhlet apparatus was used for cleaning of polyurethane foam.

Reagents :

All reagents used were of analytical reagent grade. Water used for experiments was purified by reverse osmosis with an Elix 3 system followed by deionization with an 18 M Ω cm⁻¹ deionised Milli-Q system (Millipore USA). All laboratory materials were cleaned with acid (2 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃), rinsed with Milli-Q water and stored in a laminar flow cabinet. Hexaammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate (Merck, Germany) and suprapure grade nitric acid (Merck, Germany) were used. Acetone from Merck, Germany was used. A commercially available

arsenic standard solution for AAS (1000 mg L⁻¹, Merck, Germany) was used. The working solutions were prepared daily by accurate dilution with pure water. Molybdate solution 0.05 mol L⁻¹ was prepared from hexaammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate (NH₄)₆(Mo₇O₂₄).4H₂O in water. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) 0.1% w/v was prepared in water. Before use, PVA solution was filtered through a cellulose membrane filter (pore size, 0.45 μ m; diameter, 2.5 cm). Rhodamine B solution, 12 \times 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹ was prepared in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid. Rhodamine exhibit its different forms in acid, alkali and neutral media and in this work it is prepared in acid solution.

Polyurethane foam preparation :

Open-pore polyether-type polyurethane foam (PUF) with a bulk density of 22 kg m⁻³ was cut into small square shaped pieces of 1 cm \times 1 cm \times 1 cm size and was used for this study. The foam plugs were first squeezed in acetone for 30 min to open their pores, washed with water and dried at 80 °C in an oven. The dried foam plugs were then soaked in 2 M hydrochloric acid solution for 2 h to remove all inorganic impurities, washed with water until the washing was acid free and neutral, and later dried at 80 °C in an oven. The dried plugs were soaked in acetone for 30 min to remove all organic impurities. The foam was then pressed between filter papers to remove excess acetone and dried at 80 °C and stored for further use.

General procedure :

A suitable aliquot of arsenic solution containing 0.1–5 ng mL⁻¹ As was taken in 50 mL PTFE beaker. Arsenomolybdate was formed at 1 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid and 16 \times 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ molybdate. Arsenomolybdate formed was extracted on PUF by adding 5–6 foam plugs and squeezing with a plastic plunger. After 15 min the foam plugs were washed with water and the sorbed arsenomolybdate was eluted in acetone into 25 mL calibrated flask. Ion associate between arsenomolybdate and RB was formed at 0.03 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid and 6 \times 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹ RB. To the mixture 2.5 mL of 0.1% PVA was added. The volume was made with water. The absorbance was measured at 560 nm against reagent blank since the λ_{max} of the coloured complex is found at 560 nm.

Determination of total arsenic in water samples :

Tube well water samples :

A tube well water sample was taken after running the water for 10 min. A 5.0 ml aliquot of tube well water sample was placed in a 50 ml PTFE beaker. The determination of total arsenic was then carried out as described under general procedure.

Tap water sample :

A tap water sample was collected after running water for 10 min. A 5.0 ml aliquot of tap water samples was taken in a 50 ml polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) beaker. The determination of total arsenic was done following the same as described in general procedure.

Surface water sample :

For surface water, the sample was filtered through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper and a 5.0 ml portion of the sample was treated as described in the general procedure.

Shallow water sample :

A shallow water sample was taken after running water for 10 min. A 5.0 ml aliquot of shallow water sample was placed in a 50 ml PTFE beaker. The determination of total arsenic was then carried out as described under general procedure.

Results and discussion

In our previous study²¹⁻²³ it was noted that yellow arsenomolybdate complex formed in nitric medium has a tendency to be sorbed selectively on PUF within a short period of time (< 15 min). The sorbed complex on foam matrix could be eluted with acidified acetone. In order to increase the sensitivity of the method, the eluted arsenomolybdate complex was further allowed to form an ion association complex with RB. Rhodamine B was employed as an ion associating reagent because the dye has high fluorescence intensity and stability under strongly acidic condition²⁶. The structure of Rhodamine B and its ion-association complex is shown in Fig. 1. The possible reaction mechanism for the formation of ion association complex as follows :

Rhodamine B [RhB]
 $[\text{H}_2\text{AsMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^- [\text{RhB}]^+$
 Ion association complex

Fig. 1. Structure of Rhodamine B and corresponding ion-pair complex.

The absorption spectrum of this ion-association complex has been drawn and shown in Fig. 2. It is found that the complex has maximum absorption at 560 nm. This observation leads to further investigation for establishing different parameters affecting the quantitative formation of ion association complex of arsenomolybdate with Rhodamine B.

Effect of experimental variables for the formation of ion-association complex :

Optimum conditions for the concentration of molybdate, nitric acid, amount of solid solvent (PUF) and time of extraction of arsenomolybdate on PUF, which were studied in the previous work²¹⁻²³ are adopted in the present study. A series of experiments were carried for selecting the medium acidity for the formation of ion associate of arsenomolybdate with RB using sulfuric acid and nitric acid. Ultimately nitric acid was selected because of lower value of reagent blank, a higher absorbance signal and better linearity of the calibration graph.

Effect of nitric acid concentration : Experiments were performed to see the effect of nitric acid concentration on the formation of ion associate of arsenomolybdate with RB and the results obtained are shown in Fig. 3. Highest value of the absorbance was achieved when 0.025 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid was used and the calibration graph was found to be linear. Therefore, 0.025 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid was adopted. Further increase in the nitric acid concentration lowers the absorbances because RB is converted into a protonated orange cation by an excess of nitric acid resulting in decrease in absorbances.

Fig. 2. The absorption spectrum of arsenomolybdate-Rhodamine B complex.

Fig. 3. Effect of nitric acid concentration. RB : 6×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹, PVA : 0.02% (w/v); (1) 0.025 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃, linear correlation coefficient 0.997, (2) 0.05 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃, linear correlation coefficient 0.9949, (3) 0.10 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃, linear correlation coefficient 0.9945.

Effect of PVA and its concentration : Spectrophotometric method of arsenic²⁴ based on the formation of an ion associate between arsenomolybdate anion and a cationic dye is sensitive enough. The ion associate formed between molybdate and RB tends to precipitate and the base line become very noisy and linearity of the calibration graph is disturbed. In order to stabilize the ion associate, PVA was added which prevents the precipitation of

the complex and thus base line drift is avoided. In this work, 0.01% PVA was chosen as an optimum concentration to achieve the linearity of the calibration graph and low base line noise. On increasing the concentration of PVA ($> 0.01\%$), the solution became more viscous resulting in reduced stability of background and poor linearity of the calibration graph.

Effect of Rhodamine B concentration : The effect of RB concentration was studied by varying the concentrations from 2×10^{-7} to 8×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹. The results showed that with the increase in RB concentration (Fig. 4) there is increase in absorbance. But with high RB concentration, the base line became noisy and therefore 6×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹ RB was considered to be the optimum concentration.

Calibration graph : Under the experimental conditions, a calibration graph was constructed in the concentration range 0.5 to 5 ng mL⁻¹ As using standard arsenic solution to determine the features of the method. The calibration graph showed a good linearity. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.5 to 5 ng mL⁻¹ As. The molar absorptivity at the wavelength corresponding to maximum absorbance at 560 nm was calculated by measuring the absorbance of solution at different concentration level of arsenic. The mean value of the molar

Fig. 4. Effect of Rhodamine B (RB) concentration. HNO_3 : 0.025 mol L^{-1} , PVA : $0.02\% \text{ (w/v)}$; (1) $2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ RB, linear correlation coefficient 0.9925, (2) $4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ RB, linear correlation coefficient 0.9941, (3) $6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ RB, linear correlation coefficient 0.9999, (4) $8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ RB, linear correlation coefficient 0.9952.

absorptivity was found to be $2.25 \times 10^6 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which indicates that the method is sensitive. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999. The detection limit attained by the proposed method was 0.1 ng mL^{-1} As.

Effect of foreign ions : The concentrations of some anions e.g. Cl^- , NO_2^- , Br^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} in water are in the range $0\text{--}9 \text{ pg mL}^{-1}$. The range of concentrations of some metals, such as Li, Na, Mg, Al, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Pb is $0.034\text{--}0.94 \text{ pg mL}^{-1}$ while K, Ca and Zn are present in the range $4.4\text{--}6.8 \text{ pg mL}^{-1}$ ²⁵. It is studied that there are no interference of the above mentioned anions and cations to form arsenomolybdate in

water. Only phosphate and silicate form molybdophosphate and silicomolybdate and also form ion associate with RB. The effect of phosphate can be eliminated by the addition of oxalic acid, which decomposes any molybdophosphate formed. Effect of silicate can be removed by the treatment of water sample with HF and nitric acid digestion and which remove the silica from the solution forming volatile H_2SiF_6 .

Application : Suitable and optimum analytical conditions have been established to detect arsenic in standard water sample which is shown in Table 1 and the proposed method has been verified for ground water and surface water samples (Table 2). Trace arsenic at ng mL^{-1} levels was detected in the doubly-distilled water and distilled water. Arsenic present in water samples were tested in Hydride Generated Atomic Absorption Spectrometer and the results were compared with those obtained by the present method which is shown in Table 2. The proposed method is found to be highly reliable and accompanied by good precision.

Conclusion :

In the present method, a new technique for the enrichment of ultra-trace arsenic on PUF has been successfully

Table 1. Determination of arsenic in standard samples

Sl. no.	Samples	Certified arsenic content ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	As found by proposed method ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Recovery (%)
1.	NIST1643d	56.00	55.01	98.23
2.	NIST1643e	58.98	58.20	98.68
3.	CRM 609	1.20	1.18	98.33

Table 2. Determination of arsenic in water samples

Water samples	Arsenic added (ng ml^{-1})	As 'spiked', found ^a (ng ml^{-1})		As 'unspiked', found ^a (ng ml^{-1})	
		This work	AAS	This work	AAS
		Tap water	15.0	19.5	19.7
	20.0	24.5	24.7	4.6	4.7
Tube well water	35.0	50.5	51.0	15.5	16.0
	70.0	86.0	85.9	15.9	15.8
Surface water	20.0	22.6	22.4	2.4	2.3
	25.0	27.5	27.7	2.2	2.5
Shallow water	45.0	131.5	130.5	86.5	85.5
	75.0	160.8	161.0	85.7	86.0

^aValues given represent the average of six analysis of each sample.

introduced. Sensitivity of the method has been increased by the formation of ternary complex of arsenomolybdate with RB. The method described in this study has useful application in the determination of ultra-trace arsenic in surface and ground water.

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